

AEROELASTIC TAILORING STUDY IN AIRCRAFT DESIGN

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Summary

A computer program called COSMOS has been developed by FHI under the sponsorship of MITI, which allows structure optimization under the constraints of strength, deflection and flutter velocity. This paper describes some of the research findings obtained through COSMOS development. Verification test results are also reported.

Introduction

In the aircraft preliminary design phase many requirements such as strength, deflection, flutter etc. must be considered. However to realize design requirements with conventional design methods is almost impossible. Aeroelastic tailoring technology has a great potential to reduce aircraft weight and to assist in the design of high performance aircraft. Because tailoring technology usually requires a large number of repeated calculations, the use of a computer program is mandatory. We are developing a computer program called COSMOS (COMposite Structure Multi- constrained Optimization System). The objective of the program is to be a design tool for aeroelastic tailored wings.

Outline of the program

COSMOS development began in 1981, as one of the research items set by The Research and Development Institute of Metals and Composites for Future Industries sponsored by The Agency of Industrial Science and Technology, MITI. Fig. 1 shows the history of COSMOS development. The program is able to assess and resige element dimension, such as thickness and cross sectional areas, in order to minimize the structural weight under the constraints of strength, deflection, flutter and natural frequency. Available combinations of constraints are shown in Fig. 1.

The main objective of the program is the optimization of composite laminated structures, but the optimization of metal structures is also possible.

In the optimization of the composite laminated structure, the ply orientation and the ply thickness must be determined. But in the actual design, the ply orientation is usually limited by manufacturing requirements and often determined as [0° / +30° / +60° / 90°]. Therefore the program COSMOS is written so that ply orientation data, input by a user, is not changed in the optimization process. The program outputs the element thickness of each orientation ply. This concept simplifies the program

	<u>CONSTRAINT</u>	<u>FISCAL YEAR</u>
1.	static strength	} 1981
2.	deflection	
3.	static strength + deflection	
4.	flutter speed	1982
5.	static strength + flutter speed	} 1983
6.	static strength + deflection + flutter speed	
7.	natural frequency	1984

Fig. 1 History of COSMOS Development

algorithm and the existing FEM (Finite Element Method) module could be introduced directly into the COSMOS. Last year the FEM module was replaced by the SAP-IV program.

There are many optimization methods and each method has its own merits and lack of merits. The optimization method used in COSMOS is called the optimality criterion method, because the method can handle several thousand design variables.

The optimality criterion for each constraint is as follows.

- 1) Static strength: uniform ratio of allowable and actual strain energy density for all elements

$$\left(\frac{\partial U_{act}^{(i)}}{\partial U_{all}^{(i)}} = \text{constant: where } U_{act}^{(i)}, U_{all}^{(i)} \text{ is the actual and allowable strain energy per unit mass of } i\text{-th elements respectively } \right)$$
- 2) Deflection: uniform deflection derivatives for all elements

$$\left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial w_i} = \text{constant: where } w_i \text{ is the weight of } i\text{-th elements, } \delta \text{ is deflection } \right)$$
- 3) Flutter: uniform flutter velocity derivatives for all elements

$$\left(\frac{\partial V_F}{\partial w_i} = \text{constant: where } V_F \text{ is flutter velocity } \right)$$
- 4) Frequency: uniform frequency derivatives for all elements

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial w_i} = \text{constant: where } f \text{ is the first mode frequency } \right)$$

In the strength optimization module, failure criterion of composite materials is required. But there are many criteria and no all-purpose single criterion has yet been proposed. The following four failure criteria are incorporated into the program and user can select one of them by using a program control card.

- 1) Mainmum strain theory
- 2) Mainmum stress theory
- 3) Hoffman's rule
- 4) Tsai-Wu rule

Correlation with tests

In order to correlate the analytic data of COSMOS, a test prototype was made and rigidity and vibration test were conducted.

The test model was 2 meters long simulated the inter-spar structure of a high-aspect ratio transport wing. It was designed to achieve minimum weight under the constraints of static strength and displacement. The static strength constraint was designed to endure the design loading condition of a 3.3G limit gust load. The deflection constraint was designed to reflect a zero twist angle at the free end under 1 G loading condition. The test model had a cantilever sandwich beam with CFRP (350°F cure type) laminated upper and lower tailored face plates and an aluminium core. The ply orientation of the laminates was [0° / +45° / 90°].

The analysis model of the prototype is shown in Fig. 2. Finite elements used in the analysis were QDMMEM, CTRMEM, CSHEAR and CROD, which have the same characteristics as NASTRAN. The model was divided into 972 finite elements and the thicknesses of upper and lower plate elements were resized individually in each ply orientation. After the tailoring analysis, the test model was designed with consideration to certain manufacturing requirements such as limit of ply lamination in any one direction.

The final model configuration is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows the

OBJECTIVE: Minimum Weight
 CONSTRAINT: (1) Static Strength
 (2) Twist Angle = 0
 at Section A-A

No. of Nodes : 228
 No. of Elements : 972

Fig. 2 Analysis Model

analytic values of twist angle along the span of the analyzed model and the test model. Also shown in the figure is the twist angle of the optimized model under the constraint of static strength only.

The static test was conducted to meet the design limit loading condition. Strain and displacement were measured during the test. After the static test, the vibration test was conducted and the natural frequency and mode were measured. The objective of the vibration test was to verify the normal mode analysis portion of the COSMOS program in relation to the flutter analysis module.

Fig. 5 shows the static test results compared with the predicted values by COSMOS analysis. Measured strain at the face plate falls in the region of + 15 percent of the analysis.

The difference of the twist angles between the measured and predicted values is less than one third of a degree at three different sections along the span.

Vibration test results are shown in Fig. 6. The maximum difference between the measured and analyzed values is 20 percent.

A tailoring example under three constraints

To explain the function of COSMOS, this section describes the results of an example study in which a model was optimized under three constraints.

The simple straight rectangular wing shown in Fig. 7 was analyzed in order to achieve a minimum weight under the constraints of static strength, deflection and flutter speed. Each constraint is shown as follows.

Ply Direction Zone	0°	-45°	45°	90°	Total
	①	16	5	1	1
②	13	↕	↕	↕	20
③	10	↕	↕	↕	17
④	7	↕	↕	↕	14
⑤	7	↕	↕	↕	15
⑥	4	↕	↕	↕	11
⑦	1	↕	↕	↕	8
⑧	1	3	1	1	6

Fig. 3 Configuration of the Test Model

Fig. 4 Twist Angle of the Test Model

COMPARISON OF TEST RESULTS						
STRAIN				TWIST ANGLE		
	ϵ_{TEST}	ϵ_{ANAL}	$(\epsilon_{TEST}/\epsilon_{ANAL})$	θ_{TEST}	θ_{ANAL}	$ \theta_{TEST} - \theta_{ANAL} $
①	758	675	(1.12)			
②	863	909	(0.95)	A	0.35°	0.25° (0.10°)
③	1075	1185	(0.91)	B	0.55°	0.32° (0.23°)
④	1200	1404	(0.85)	C	0.77°	0.47° (0.30°)
⑤	1223	1236	(0.99)			
⑥	1225	1229	(1.00)			

Fig. 5 Comparison of Strain and Twist Angle

Fig. 6 Comparison of Frequency

- 1) Every element should have a positive margin of safety (M. S.) for the design loading condition. (3.6 G limit maneuver load, 79,400N ultimate load per wing)
- 2) Tip twist angle at 1 G level flight should be one third of the twist angle of the structure optimized for the strength constraint only.
- 3) Flutter speed should be 300 m/s.

When this model was analyzed the first time, the design flutter speed of 180 m/s was used, however, the speed was too slow and not critical as an optimization constraint. Therefore the flutter speed requirement of 300 m/s was decided upon. (based on research observations)

The only elements resized during optimization process were the upper and lower CFRP laminated plates, which had the ply orientation of [0° / +45° / 90°]. Spars and ribs were of aluminium and were not resized. The failure criterion used was the Tsai-Wu rule, where the experimental constant F_{12} was set equal to zero. The analyzed model had 28 node points and 80 finite elements; including 48 membranes modeling the upper and lower laminated plates.

Fig. 8 shows the iteration history of the element thickness. The first twenty times involved resizing for static strength constraint only, while the remaining 44 times involved resizing for all three constraints. Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. show the history of the total mass of optimized elements and the history of flutter velocity and twist angle respectively.

Effectiveness of optimization ---- numerical example

To demonstrate the effectiveness of structural optimization on weight saving, the simple wing model (explained in the previous section) was analyzed. The difference between the two test model is as follows.

Fig. 7 Rectangular Wing Model

Fig. 8 History of the Ply Thickness in Each Bay

Fig. 9 History of Total Mass

Fig. 10 History of Flutter Speed and Twist Angle

- 1) only the flutter constraint was used.
 - 2) required flutter velocity was 330 m/s instead of 300 m/s.
- The model configuration was the same as shown in Fig. 7.

Analysis was done in two stages. The first was to measure the weight of composite laminates which simulated isotropic material. The first analysis model had the ply orientation of $[0^\circ / +45^\circ / 90^\circ]$. The thickness changing ratio was determined by the program automatically. Through the optimization process, the ratio of the thickness of each ply was constant. The constant value was 25%. The model was analyzed to achieve the minimum weight of isotropically laminated composite material.

The second analysis model had the same ply orientation as the first one, but the element thickness was resized on an individual basis to achieve minimum weight.

The result of the first analysis is shown in Fig. 11. The abscissa of the figure is the ratio of total weight increase. The optimum structure weight of the isotropically laminated composite is 4 percent heavier than the initial structure. On the other hand, Fig. 12 shows the result of the second analysis, where the abscissa is the ratio of weight decrease: a 17 percent weight decrease could be achieved from the initial structure weight. Therefore more than a 20 percent weight saving could be possible through laminate thickness optimization of this simple wing model.

Moreover the rigidity ratio (E/ρ) of CFRP (isotropically laminated plates) is about 53 percent larger than that of aluminium alloys. The possible weight of the conventional metal structure could be calculated from the weight of the isotropically laminated composite model. The result is shown in Fig. 13. The weight shown includes weights of leading and trailing edges, spars and ribs. Model B (isotropically laminated composites) shows a 22% weight saving from Model C (conventional aluminium), while Model A (optimum layer thickness for each ply) shows a 39% weight saving.

Fig. 11 Weight Change of the Wing Model (B)
(isotropically laminated CFRP)

Fig. 12 Weight Change of the Wing Model (A)
(optimum ply thickness)

Fig. 13 Effectiveness of Optimization

Fig. 14 Box Beam Model

Fig. 15 Effectiveness of Matrix Improvement

Potential weight saving by matrix improvement

There is a possibility to achieve stronger composite lamination by improving matrix elongation. To demonstrate this possibility, a simple box beam was analyzed. The model size was 600mm(L) x 400mm(W) x 100mm(H). The upper and lower plates consisted of laminated composites. Ply orientation was [0° / +45° / 90°]. (see Fig. 14)

The thickness of each ply was resized iteratively so as to minimize total beam weight under the static strength constraint. The strength constraint was such that the box beam structure should have positive margins of safety when a 490,000N.mm bending moment per unit length was applied at the free end. The optimization analysis was done changing the allowable matrix elongation parametrically.

Fig. 15. shows the weight ratio of upper and lower plates after the optimization. 100 percent in the figure means the optimized beam weight calculated using the value of matrix elongation of 0.005. A weight saving of more than 25percent would be achieved if the allowable matrix elongation

was improved from the current value of 0.005 to 0.01. While only about a 12 percent weight saving would be achieved if the allowable fiber elongation was improved from the current value of 0.01 to 0.02.

The region below the dash line in Fig. 13. shows the area where the compression side of the beam is critical. The improvement of allowable compression of the matrix along with the improvement of allowable tension is required before greater weight saving can be achieved.

This result shows that the improvement of matrix elongation is more effective than fiber improvement for possible weight saving.

Improvement of strength optimality criterion

In the first stage of COSMOS development, FSD (Fully Stressed Design) was used for the strength optimality criterion. In the course of development, a study of an anisotropic model revealed that FSD is inadequate for the anisotropic optimization. The thickness of elements with the fiber direction perpendicular to the loading direction were increasing as the iteration continued, while the thickness of elements with fiber direction parallel to the loading direction approached zero.

The reason for this phenomenon was due to the difference between the allowable stresses of composite in the two directions. The allowable stress perpendicular to the loading direction was very low and the margins of safety for the elements were lower than those of the elements of which the fiber direction was parallel to the loading direction. Therefore the thickness of the weak elements increased according to the FSD resizing rule and the phenomenon described above occurred.

To avoid this insufficiency, a new strength criterion was used in place of FSD. The new criterion is the principle that the ratio of the strain energy density to the allowable strain energy density is uniform when the structure is optimum. This new criterion is now used in COSMOS and gives good results for several anisotropic model studies.

Conclusion

The composite structure optimization program COSMOS has been developed and used for several tailoring problems in past three years. The major advantage of this system is that it can handle several requirements of aircraft design and show the possible alternative structural dimensions automatically.

The following four constraints are handled by COSMOS at the present time.

- 1) static strength
- 2) deflection
- 3) flutter speed
- 4) frequency

Other requirements such as buckling, thermal stress, fatigue, impact etc. are also important in aerospace structures. These constraints will be incorporated into the system step by step.

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